

Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering

Research Data Management Policy

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Preface

The Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering (IDE) recognizes the growing importance for research data management in response to the increased complexity of research in digital environments. This policy is intended to provide guidance for design researchers, and it reflects good practices for working with research data currently handled within the field of design. It defines data management roles and responsibilities of the different stakeholders within the faculty and is affiliated with the central [TU Delft Research Data Framework Policy](#). Terminology used in this policy is supported by the definitions given in the framework and are supplemented by online guidance on data management provided by TU Delft and related policies and documents.

This document is motivated by the belief that good data practices lead to research that is more time- and cost-efficient, and it is inspired by principles that research data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). It builds upon the articles for scientific conduct presented in the [Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) and [recommendations on the future of scholarly publishing and communication](#) issued by the European Commission.

This policy cultivates:

- Good practice for ensuring that scientific arguments and results are transparent and, if applicable, reproducible in the long term
- Increased exposure of academic work of researchers within IDE and potential credit for time and effort devoted to the collection and organization of authentic, quality data
- Responsible management of research data, including the safe storage of research data and protection of intellectual capital developed by members of the faculty
- Awareness and understanding of demands of funders and publishers with respect to research data management and sharing

This policy recognises that:

- Individual departments and research groups have varied working practices and processes by which the day-to-day management of data is conducted
- Data management constitutes the entire process of managing research data from its collection/creation to its re-use and preservation. It is not synonymous with Open Data or Open Science in general. While it is considered beneficial to publish research data openly, there are several valid factors, such as ethical, legal or reasons related to intellectual property rights, which may make data unsuitable for open sharing
- Design research touches upon, or intersects with, numerous academic disciplines, and materials recognized as research data differ between these disciplines. In this policy research data is broadly defined as whatever sources serve as evidence for research findings. These include, but are not limited to: interviews, surveys, assessments of material properties, sensor data, co-creation actions, project maps, observation notes, etc. Source code, experimental notes, statistical analyses, protocols, and other forms of information supporting traditional publication are also within the scope of this policy

Roles and Responsibilities

The Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering Research Data Management Policy only specifies the roles and responsibilities of faculty-specific stakeholders. The [TU Delft Research Data Framework Policy](#) should be consulted about the roles of the Library, ICT Department, University Services and the Executive Board at TU Delft.

Principal investigators are responsible for:

- Ensuring that all members of the research group (including PhD students) are aware of the FAIR data principles and are appropriately trained to effectively manage research data, and that they adhere to the expectations outlined within this policy
- Ensuring that, in consultation with the faculty contracts manager and, where desired, the data steward, any agreements with external funding agencies, commercial companies or other third parties follow the guidelines laid out in this data policy
- Assessing the appropriate degree and means of data sharing, as openly as possible and as closed as necessary according to contractual obligations or other relevant conditions
- Budgeting for the costs of data management into financial project planning at the proposal stage

PhD Supervisors are responsible for:

- Supporting their PhD students in preparation of a written data management plan for managing research outputs within the first 12 months of the PhD study
- Ensuring that PhD students attend relevant training on data management
- Ensuring that their PhD students make all data and code underlying their completed PhD theses appropriately documented and accessible for at least 15 years from the end of the research project, in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). This data should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary

Individual Researchers are responsible for:

- Ensuring that research data, code and any other materials needed to validate research findings and, where feasible, reproduce them, are appropriately documented, stored and shared in a research data repository in accordance with the FAIR principles for at least 15 years from the end of the research project, unless there are valid reasons not to do so
- Should data not be made available in a repository, ensure that the data management plan and any research publications resulting from the project have a statement explaining what additional datasets/materials exist, who can use the data and under what circumstances
- Understanding who owns research data resulting from their projects and what that implies in terms of data management, particularly sharing and publishing

In addition, PhD students are responsible for:

- Developing a written data management strategy for managing research outputs within the first 12 months of the PhD study
- Attending relevant training in data management
- Ensuring that all data and code underlying completed PhD theses are appropriately documented and accessible for at least 10 years following the deposit of their written thesis, unless there are valid reasons which make research data unsuitable for sharing

Research Management Staff (Valorization, Contracts Managers, Data Steward) are responsible for:

- Facilitating the development, review and implementation of the faculty's data management policy and guidelines
- Creating awareness and explain to researchers the added value of good data management
- Assisting researchers in planning the collection, management, and publication of data in research projects and liaise with other faculty and university stakeholders (such as Legal services, ICT, Human Research Ethics Committee) as required
- Advising researchers on the content of data management plans and with budgeting for research data management costs in their grant applications
- Identifying needs for and assist in incorporating data management practice into existing education and training as needed

The Faculty Dean is responsible for:

- Ensuring that good data management practices remain part of the vision for research conducted within the faculty
- Ensuring that within their faculty there is appropriate infrastructure and tools for researchers to put good data management into practice

Department Heads are responsible for:

- Ensuring awareness of good data management practices among all researchers and students within the department
- Developing effective strategies for monitoring and review of data management practices
- Taking responsibility of data for projects during exceptional circumstances

Heads of Sections are responsible for:

- Encouraging individual research groups to adhere to and build upon accepted practices for good data management and FAIR data for design research (or to develop them if disciplinary standards do not exist)
- Encouraging individual research groups to adopt good data management practices among all researchers and students within the section
- Working with the faculty data steward to develop practical solutions for data management within the section, and determine/benchmark usefulness of the RDM guidelines